

Fig 1 Zero order rate plots at 35°
 [NBS] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M, [HClO₄] = 2.5 × 10⁻³ M
 [Hg(OAc)₂] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ M [Cyclohexanone] = 0.5, 1.0
 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5 × 10⁻³ M in 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 respectively

concentration was studied. An increase in hydrogen ion concentration increased the zero order rate constants linearly (Table 2) and the average value of $k_1 = k_0/[HClO_4]$ was found as (3.54 ± 0.18) and $(5.70 \pm 0.15) \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ at 35° and 40° respectively.

10 ³ [HClO ₄] M	k ₀ × 10 ⁷ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹ 35°	k ₀ × 10 ⁷ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹ 40°	k ₁ = k ₀ /[HClO ₄] sec ⁻¹ 35°	k ₁ = k ₀ /[HClO ₄] sec ⁻¹ 40°
2.0	7.27	11.7	3.63	5.85
2.5	8.65	14.2	3.46	5.68
3.0	10.1	17.1	3.36	5.70
4.0	14.9	22.2	3.72	5.55
5.0	17.7	28.7	3.54	5.74

Addition of NaClO₄ from nil to 1M and mercuric acetate and succinimide from nil to 0.01M showed no effect on the reaction rate. However, addition of methanol showed a positive influence on the reaction rate (Table 3).

TABLE-3
EFFECT OF METHANOL ON REACTION RATE AT 35°

[NBS] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M [Cyclohexanone] = 1.2 × 10⁻³ M
 [HClO₄] = 2.5 × 10⁻³ M and [Hg(OAc)₂] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ M

MeOH %	k ₀ × 10 ⁷ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
0	8.65
10	9.35
20	10.3
30	11.2
40	12.3

Various rate parameters viz energy of activation ($\Delta E^\ddagger$), frequency factor (A), entropy of activation ($\Delta S^\ddagger$), heat of activation ($\Delta H^\ddagger$) and free energy of activation ($\Delta F^\ddagger$) were computed from the rate study measurement carried out at five different temperatures (30–50) and the average values were found as 20.1 kcal mol⁻¹, $(5.40 \pm 0.11) \times 10^{11} \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$, $(-5.83 \pm 0.03) \text{ e.u.}$, $19.5 \pm 0.1 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ and $21.4 \pm 0.1 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ respectively.

Discussion

It is well known that NBS exists in acid media in following equilibria,

and thus the oxidising species could be either NBS itself or Br⁺ or NBSH⁺,

However, in presence of mercuric acetate Br⁻ is fixed up as HgBr₄²⁻ or unionised HgBr₂. Thus in the present studies any oxidation by free bromine is completely excluded.

It is seen that the order in NBS is zero and according to Littler³ in such a case with 2-electron oxidants, the rates of oxidation are related to rates of enolisation. The acid catalysed oxidation of ketone clearly points out to the fact that the protonated form of the ketone is involved in the oxidation process. The accepted mechanism of formation of the protonated enol is as follows,

This protonated enol formed in step (6) reacts with any of the species derived from NBS viz NBS, Br⁺ or NBSH⁺ in fast steps to give the final product.

Summarising,

where X^+ represents the intermediate complex

As the steps (8) and (9) are much faster in comparison to (7), it is difficult to argue about the relative merits of NBS species taking part in these steps. But, still, the balance lies more in favour of NBS itself rather than $NBSH^+$ or Br^+ as the reaction of SH^+ and Br^+ or $NBSH^+$ (step 8) would be a reaction between two positive charged ions and may not be faster in comparison to (7) as suggested.

The proposed mechanism gives rise to the following rate law,

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [NBS] = 2k_1 [S] [H^+] \quad (10)$$

which is consistent with the observed kinetics. The observed positive effect of methanol agrees well for a rate-determining reaction between a positive ion and a dipole. The average value of specific rate constant $k_s = k_2/[H^+] [S]$ has been obtained as $(3.46 \pm 0.11) \times 10^{-3} \text{ l. mole}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ at 35° .

Thus it is clear that NBS oxidation of cyclohexanone involves the formation of protonated enol in a slow and rate determining step, which is subsequently oxidised by NBS to products in fast steps.

Acknowledgements

Thanks are due to UGC and CSIR, New Delhi for financial assistance to JNT and AKB

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